

NUMERICAL METHODOLOGY FOR THE PREDICTION OF THE LOCAL BOND-SLIP LAW FOR CONCRETE ELEMENTS STRENGTHENED WITH FRP

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ABSTRACT

The characterization of an accurate local bond-slip model is one of the fundamental challenges in modelling fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) strengthened reinforced concrete (RC). This paper presents a novel method for developing and validating an accurate bond-slip model. It utilizes a numerical procedure based on the finite difference method and incorporates a metaheuristic optimization algorithm, so that no specific bond-slip law shape is needed. The presented methodology also enables modelling tests with premature failure before reaching the maximum load. The obtained results confirm the accuracy of the methodology. Due to space limitations, only results related to NSM specimens are presented.

KEYWORDS

Bond behaviour; Numerical modelling; Metaheuristic algorithm; Strengthening.

INTRODUCTION

Externally bonded reinforcement (EBR) fibre reinforced polymer (FRP), which was introduced in the field of civil engineering almost three decades ago, stands as one of the most efficient methods for strengthening existing reinforced concrete (RC) structures (Hollaway & Teng, 2008). This method involves the application of FRP composites onto the tensile face of concrete structures using a structural adhesive (Teng et al., 2002). However, a common issue encountered with this method is the premature debonding or delamination of the FRP, occurring before the materials reach their full capacity. This significant problem has led to extensive investigations into the bond behaviour between FRP composites and concrete. In this regard, researchers have conducted numerous experimental (Martinelli et al., 2011; Shi et al., 2019) and theoretical (Li et al., 2022; Lu et al., 2005; Yuan et al., 2004) works to study the importance of different parameters that may contribute to premature debonding.

Due to the premature debonding failure of EBR systems, various alternative FRP-strengthening methods have been proposed, such as near surface mounted (NSM), externally bonded reinforcement on grooves (EBROG) and externally bonded reinforcement in grooves (EBRIG), aiming to improve the bond strength of FRP-concrete bonded joint (Dai Minh Nguyen et al., 2001; Garden-F & Hollaway, 1998; Liu et al., 2006.; Mostofinejad & Mahmoudabadi, 2010.; Mostofinejad & Shameli, 2013; Phalguni Mukhopadhyaya & Swamy, 2001; Seracino et al., 2012a). Detecting and decoupling the various bond mechanisms activated by each of these methods can be a challenging task, as they may diverge from one another. This complexity highlights the need for a comprehensive study to accurately analyse and propose an appropriate bond-slip law.

Focusing on the NSM strengthening systems, their bond performance may be affected by different parameters, such as FRP (rod/strip) mechanical properties and dimensions, adhesion properties of the three involved materials, concrete mechanical properties, and groove dimensions, among others (Al-Saadi & Al-Mahaidi, 2016). Therefore, the proposed bond-slip models presented in existing works were

obtained based on specific set of variables, so that they may not be considered fully comprehensive (Al-Saadi & Al-Mahaidi, 2016; Borchert & Zilch, 2008; Seracino et al., 2012a).

Despite the numerous bond-slip models proposed by researchers, developing a general method to obtain a bond-slip model that incorporates various variables through conventional methods is challenging and time-consuming. One way to reduce the computational time is using a metaheuristic algorithm called Teaching-Learning-based-optimization (TLBO). TLBO, previously introduced by Rao et al. in (2011), utilizes stochastic movement in multiple directions, guided by different strategies in the teacher and learner phases. The advantage of TLBO is its parameter-free nature, making it applicable as a metaheuristic optimizer for various engineering problems. Rao et al. (2012) applied TLBO to optimize large-scale nonlinear problems and it has also been employed for the geometry and size optimization of various truss structures (Artar & Carbas, 2021; Degertekin & Hayalioglu, 2013; Makiabadi et al., 2013). Additionally, Jianli Jia (2022) studied the debonding strength of FRP composites using novel models of Extreme Learning Machine (ELM) in cooperation with TLBO, and Viet-Linh Tran (2023) developed artificial neural network (ANN) and TLBO models for predicting the reinforcing bar bonding failure stress. In this work, TLBO is employed to predict the local bond-slip law of various NSM FRP-to-concrete bonded joints using a combination of a finite difference method and a metaheuristic algorithm. To validate the method's performance, synthetic data is generated using an ABAQUS Finite Element Model (FEM), which is then compared with the TLBO method's prediction to assess its accuracy.

METHODOLOGY

This paper aims to predict the local bond-slip law in NSM FRP strengthening systems from the load-slip curve of a pull-out test. A numerical procedure based on the finite difference method is proposed to solve the differential equation representing the bond behaviour (Gómez et al., 2020). The procedure is integrated into a metaheuristic algorithm's objective function. In order to assess the method's performance, synthetic data is generated using an ABAQUS FEM. This synthetic data is then used to validate the TLBO method's prediction by comparing the two sets of results.

Overview of teaching-learning-based optimization

The TLBO algorithm, previously proposed by Rao et al. (2011), is a teaching-learning process inspired algorithm that draws inspiration from the influence of a teacher on the learners in a class. The algorithm comprises two fundamental learning modes: (i) learning from the teacher (the teacher phase) and (ii) learning through interaction with other learners (the learner phase).

In this optimization algorithm, the population is represented by a group of learners, and the various subjects offered to the learners correspond to the different design variables of the optimization problem. The result of a learner is equivalent to the 'fitness' value of the optimization problem. Within the population, the best solution is considered as the teacher. The design variables correspond to the parameters involved in the objective function of the given optimization problem, and the best solution represents the optimal value of the objective function.

In the Teacher phase, a highly knowledgeable individual, $X_{Teacher}$, imparts knowledge to the learners with the goal of improving the overall performance of the group, as expressed by the following relation:

$$X_{new,i} = X_i + rand * (X_{Teacher} - round(1 + rand) * X_{Mean}) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

The function "rand" is a random number generator that produces a value within the range (0, 1) when called. X_{Mean} represents the average results of the learners in the respective subject.

During the learner phase, students can enhance their grades through peer learning. This implementation applies to randomly selected student pairs, following the provided formulation.

$$X_{new,i} = X_i + \beta * rand * (X_j - X_i), \\ \text{if } X_j \text{ better than } X_i \text{ then } \beta = 1, \text{ otherwise } \beta = -1 \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

The entire process repeats for a predetermined number of iterations, N_{Main} , and at the end, the individual with the best performance is declared as the optimal solution.

Finite element model

To validate this method, synthetic data of virtual pull-out tests generated using ABAQUS Finite Element (FE) program is required as an input. The FE numerical model comprises a rectangular concrete prism, a CFRP strip, and an adhesive part, with the boundary constraints shown in Figure 1 (Barahona et al., 2022). The model uses a regular mesh with a maximum element size of 10 mm for the concrete part, 2 mm for the CFRP strip, and 0.8 mm for the adhesive parts. A fine mesh was selected to enhance resolution in the epoxy adhesive region, which experiences higher stress concentrations and contains the cohesive interface (no perfect bond) between the adhesive and the FRP.

Figure 1: Boundary conditions of the model

In this study, three different local bond-slip models (Figure 2), based on the Bilinear (Seracino et al., 2012b) and Bilinear-friction laws, are considered to characterize the cohesive interaction laws at the adhesive bond line of NSM FRP systems. These bond-slip models are incorporated into the ABAQUS finite element analysis platform. For each bond-slip model, three different bond lengths are investigated: longer than the effective bond length (300mm), shorter than the effective bond length (100mm), and very short bond length (40mm) (see Figure 3).

Figure 2: Bond-slip models (cohesive interaction) used in the FEM numerical study

Figure 3: Models of single shear test specimens of NSM for the three bond lengths

The materials are assumed to be elastic and isotropic. The cohesive interface between the adhesive and the FRP is the only one experiencing damage. The concrete properties are determined based on Eurocode 2 equations (CEN, E., 2004), resulting in a compressive strength of 24 MPa, an elastic modulus of 29 GPa, and a Poisson's ratio of 0.11. Additionally, the characteristics of the epoxy and FRP material are provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of FRP and epoxy

Components	Dimension (mm)	Elastic Modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)
Carbon FRP strip	2.8×10^3	170 ^a	2800 ^a
Resin 220 HP	---	7.1 ^a	15 ^a

^a Provided by the manufacturer (S&P).

The concrete block has dimensions of 150×150×400 mm and features a groove with a thickness of 10 mm and a width of 15 mm. Additionally, the bond length has been set to three different lengths: 300 mm, 100 mm, and 40 mm.

Load–slip response for different local bond–slip laws

The combination of three bond lengths and three bond-slip laws gives a total of 9 simulations. From those simulations, a total of 9 load-slip curves were obtained, which are depicted in Figure 4. It is clear that the shape of local bond-slip models greatly influences the overall behaviour of the bonded joint, resulting in distinct load-slip curves (Gómez et al., 2020). Additionally, for the models with a bond length of 300 mm, the load-slip curve shows a maximum load followed by a plateau stage, indicating that this bond length exceeds the effective bond length. As expected, this is not occurring with the other simulations, as the bond lengths are shorter than the effective bond length.

Figure 4: Numerical load-slip curves (Abaqus outputs)

Numerical prediction of local bond-slip laws by TLBO

The numerical procedure used in this study is based on the method developed by Javier Gomez et al. in (2020). Traditionally, the common approach has been to assume a specific bond-slip behaviour, such as linear, linear with friction, nonlinear, etc., and then adjust the model's parameters to fit the load-slip curve. However, this present work offers a distinct advantage by allowing the flexibility in obtaining the bond-slip shape. This means that the new method is not limited to a specific shape and can be freely polygonal in shape.

Governing equation

The numerical model used in this study employs the finite difference method to solve the governing equation of the bonded joint for any local bond-slip law. The bond length (L_b) is discretized into small increments of length $\Delta x = L_b/n$, and the equilibrium equations are evaluated at defined position points (x) (Figure 5). The procedure follows an incremental slip methodology, calculating the slip and load transmission between adjacent sections as it progresses from the loaded end to the free end.

Figure 5: Scheme of the discretization along the FRP

The governing differential equation for the bond-slip behaviour of the FRP-to-concrete bonded joint is:

$$\frac{d^2s(x)}{dx^2} - \tau(s) * L_{per} \left(\frac{1}{E_f * A_f} - \frac{1}{E_c * A_c} \right) = 0, \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where E_f is the modulus of elasticity of the FRP, A_f is the cross-section of the FRP, $\tau(s)$ is the local bond-slip law of the joint, L_{per} refers to the perimeter of the interface failure layer, E_c is the modulus of elasticity of the concrete and A_c refers to the area of concrete.

The iterative process calculates the load at each point along the FRP using Eq. 4. Starting from the loaded end, the process calculates strain in the FRP (ε_f), strain in the concrete (ε_c), and bond shear stress (τ) using the bond-slip law. Increments of load are applied until convergence is achieved, indicated by ε_f at the free end approaching zero. The procedure is repeated for different slip values, generating the complete load-slip curve.

$$P(j, i) = P(j, i - 1) - \tau(j, i - 1) * L_{per} * Dx, \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

The iteration number, denoted by 'j', represents the current iteration, while 'i' refers to each position point in the process.

Problem formulation for continuous load-slip fitting minimization

The problem of minimizing the difference in the fit of the load-slip curve, with the aim of accurately predicting the polygonal shape of the bond-slip model, can be formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Find } X &= [\tau_1, \dots, \tau_u, S_1, \dots, S_v] \\ \text{to minimize } F(X) &= \left| \sum_{p=1}^{np} (F_p^{EXP} - F_p^{Theo}) \right| \\ \text{Subject to:} \\ x_{l \min} &\leq x_l \leq x_{l \max} \quad l=1, \dots, u+v \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where τ_n and S_m represents the shear and slip variables of the bond-slip model, respectively, and $f(x)$ is the objective function to be minimized; np represents the number of data points in the load-slip curve and F_p^{Theo} and F_p^{EXP} correspond to the numerical and experimental load values at the p th point, respectively. In this case, and because synthetic data generated from a FEM model is being used, the experimental values to be assumed in this fitting process correspond to the load numerically obtained from the Abaqus analysis, which is considered a fixed input. Finally, the algorithm determines the values of variables u and v , representing shear and slip variables respectively. The governing equation of the finite difference method is then utilized to generate a load-slip curve, which is compared to the fixed input curve obtained from Abaqus. The optimization procedure aims to minimize the differences between the fixed input and current load-slip curves. Ultimately, the bond-slip curve corresponding to the best-fitted load-slip curve is obtained and presented as the representative bond-slip law for the bond behaviour of the bonded joint. The accuracy of the methodology can be assessed by comparing the load-slip curve obtained from Abaqus, which is used as an input in the fitting strategy, with the load-slip curve obtained when modelling the bond problem using the proposed bond-slip law.

RESULTS

In this section, results on the application of TLBO algorithm are presented in terms of predicted bond-slip laws. In this study, the method considers 14 free points as variables to form 13-line segments of the bond-slip model. Twelve of the fourteen variables represent shear values, while the remaining two variables represent slip S_1 and S_{final} values, that represent the slips at the maximum shear stress and the final zero shear stress, respectively. The difference between these two slips is divided into 12 parts to obtain the corresponding (equally distributed) slips (corresponding to each shear value). The TLBO algorithm is utilized to optimize these points and achieve the best fit for the load-slip curve. The proposed method's performance is evaluated by comparing the load-slip curves obtained from Abaqus simulations for NSM strengthening with different bond lengths.

Long bond length ($L_b=300$ mm)

Predictions of bond-slip laws for specimens having a bond length larger than the effective bond length are presented in this section. The assumed surface interaction laws (dashed-green lines) and the corresponding load-slip curves of the bonded joint (dashed red lines) are presented in Figures 5-7. Load-slip (synthetic) data presented in Figures 5-7 (dashed red line) is used as an input for the presented methodology. Finally, solid blue lines correspond to the predicted bond-slip laws and solid black lines correspond to the optimized load-slip curves.

Table 2 presents the fixed parameters defined when applying the TLBO algorithm, where P_{TLBO} refers to population size and N_{Iter} refers to the total number of iterations. During optimization, the shear value variables are constrained between τ_{min} and τ_{max} , while the slip value variables are constrained between S_{Min} and S_{Max} .

Table 2: Variable limits and TLBO Control parameters for 300 mm bond length

P_{TLBO}	N_{Iter}	τ_{Max} (MPa)	τ_{Min} (MPa)	S_{1-Max} (mm)	S_{I-Min} (mm)	$S_{final-Max}$ (mm)	$S_{final-Min}$ (mm)
400	200	11	0.1	0.3	0.01	Max ^a	0.1

^a corresponding to the maximum slip of the load-slip curve input

Table 3 presents the best variables achieved by the TLBO algorithm, along with the Area Error, defined as the ratio between the difference of areas beneath the two load-slip curves and the area of the input curve. This error, therefore, represents the accuracy of the optimized load-slip curve obtained by the TLBO method compared to the synthetic data generated by ABAQUS. It indicates how well the optimized curve fits the synthetic data curve.

Table 3: Optimum results for 300 mm bond length

Design variables	Bond-slip model 1	Bond-slip model 2	Bond-slip model 3
τ_1 (MPa)	10.12	10.49	10.62
τ_2 (MPa)	9.28	7.42	9.91
τ_3 (MPa)	8.29	5.64	10.12
τ_4 (MPa)	7.44	5.49	10.08
τ_5 (MPa)	6.71	5.59	10.01
τ_6 (MPa)	5.89	5.58	10.10
τ_7 (MPa)	4.95	5.52	10.00
τ_8 (MPa)	4.25	5.64	9.92
τ_9 (MPa)	3.40	5.47	9.91
τ_{10} (MPa)	2.51	5.65	7.81
τ_{11} (MPa)	1.70	3.55	5.13
τ_{12} (MPa)	0.95	2.08	3.08
S_1 (mm)	0.17	0.18	0.18
S_{final} (mm)	1.30	1.30	1.29
Area error (%)	0.11	0.09	0.08

Figures 5-7 illustrate the comparison between the load-slip curves obtained by the TLBO method and the output load-slip curves from Abaqus. A close agreement is observed between the fitted response and the numerical values, resulting in an accurate prediction of bond behaviour that shows good agreement with the bond slip input to Abaqus. In all cases, there is a close prediction of the maximum shear stress (τ_l), as well as of the corresponding slip (S_l) and the slip corresponding to zero shear stress (S_{final}), indicating accurate modelling of the bond-slip shape.

Figure 5: Load-slip curve and bond-slip law for bond-slip model 1

Figure 6: Load-slip curve and bond-slip law for bond-slip model 2

Figure 7: Load-slip curve and bond-slip law for bond-slip model 3

Short bond length ($L_b = 100$ mm and 40 mm)

This section presents predictions of bond-slip laws for specimens with a bond length shorter than the effective bond length. The reduced bond length prevents the load from reaching its maximum capacity. Therefore, it is important to assess the accuracy of the method in predicting the bond-slip model and load-slip curve before reaching the maximum load. Similar as in previous case, some parameters are needed to be fixed for the application of the TLBO algorithm, as presented in Table 4, where the population size and total number of iterations remain the same as in the previous example.

Table 4: Variable limits and TLBO Control parameters for 100 mm and 40 mm bond length

P_{TLBO}	N_{Iter}	τ_{Max} (MPa)	τ_{Min} (MPa)	S_l -Max (mm)	S_l -Min (mm)	S_{final} -Max (mm)	S_{final} -Min (mm)
400	200	11	0.1	0.3	0.01	1.5	0.1

Table 5 presents the best variables achieved by the TLBO algorithm, along with the Area error.

Table 5: Optimum results for 40 mm and 100 mm bond length

Design variables	40 mm bond length			100 mm bond length		
	Bond-slip model 1	Bond-slip model 2	Bond-slip model 3	Bond-slip model 1	Bond-slip model 2	Bond-slip model 3
τ_1 (MPa)	10.00	9.99	10.05	9.99	9.94	10.06
τ_2 (MPa)	9.16	7.90	10.03	9.19	8.10	10.02
τ_3 (MPa)	8.34	5.57	10.03	8.35	5.59	10.05
τ_4 (MPa)	7.50	5.56	10.05	7.49	5.55	10.06
τ_5 (MPa)	6.68	5.59	10.05	6.69	5.59	10.06
τ_6 (MPa)	5.83	5.57	10.05	5.84	5.58	10.05
τ_7 (MPa)	5.00	5.57	10.03	4.99	5.57	10.05
τ_8 (MPa)	4.17	5.56	10.03	4.18	5.58	10.01
τ_9 (MPa)	3.34	5.64	9.95	3.32	5.55	9.95
τ_{10} (MPa)	2.51	5.41	7.42	2.51	5.61	7.52
τ_{11} (MPa)	1.67	3.57	4.96	1.67	3.75	5.01
τ_{12} (MPa)	0.85	1.82	2.49	0.85	2.07	2.50
S_l (mm)	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17
S_{final} (mm)	1.30	1.30	1.30	1.30	1.29	1.30
Area error (%)	0.01	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.19	0.00

Figures 8-10 compare the predicted bond-slip law of the TLBO method with the surface interaction law used in the numerical FEM models. Besides, a comparison of the synthetic data on load-slip curves obtained from FEM models and the optimized load-slip curve of the TLBO method is also presented. These figures demonstrate the TLBO method's ability to accurately predict the bond-slip characteristics, even with bond lengths shorter than the effective bond length.

Figure 8: Load-slip curve and bond-slip law for bond-slip model 1

Figure 9: Load-slip curve and bond-slip law for bond-slip model 2

Figure 10: Load-slip curve and bond-slip law for bond-slip model 3

Unexpected premature failure in a specimen with 300 mm bond length

In real experimental tests, unexpected problems can arise, leading to premature failures and incomplete tests. These issues may include machine malfunctions, problems with data acquisition, or other unforeseen challenges. In such cases, it would be interesting to obtain the bond behaviour of these tests even with incomplete data, to avoid wasting researchers' efforts and materials. To assess the feasibility of obtaining the bond-slip law with incomplete data, the synthetic data for three load-slip curves with a bond length of 300 mm, generated using three different local bond-slip laws in the Abaqus FEM model, is utilized. For each bond-slip model, data on load-slip curve is limited to different points. For the case of bond-slip model 1, data has been set to be available until a 91% of its maximum load (P_u). Besides, for the bond-slip models 2 and 3, data is limited until 89% and 94% of their maximum load, respectively. The variable limits and TLBO control parameters can be found in Table 2.

Figures 11-13 compare the predicted surface interaction law of the TLBO method with the one used in Abaqus. Although it is not possible to predict the whole bond-slip curve, it is clear that the methodology provides accurate results. This is evidence of the trustworthiness of the methodology in predicting the bond behaviour of the bonded joint even before completing the entire test.

Figure 11: Load-slip curve and bond-slip law for bond-slip model 1 (failure in 91% of P_u)

Figure 12: Load-slip curve and bond-slip law for bond-slip model 2 (failure in 89% of P_u)

Figure 13: Load-slip curve and bond-slip law for bond-slip model 3 (failure in 94% of P_u)

CONCLUSION

The presented work introduces a new tool for predicting the local bond-slip law of FRP-strengthened RC elements, aiming to overcome the limitations of existing methods. To this end, the presented methodology provides flexibility in selecting the bond-slip shape and solves the differential equation that characterizes the bond behaviour of the FRP-to-concrete joint. Based on presented results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- A close agreement is observed between the results obtained from this new method and the finite element model for the three different bond-slip model examples. These comparison demonstrates the methodology capability to accurately predict the bond-slip models by providing the freedom to obtain the desired bond slip shape without relying on a predefined shear slip shape.
- Additionally, the presented methodology is able to successfully predict the accurate bond behaviour in those cases with insufficient bond length, by predicting the bond behaviour based on the premature descent of the load-slip curve.
- Furthermore, the methodology is also valid to accurately predict the bond-slip model for tests that experienced unexpected failure before reaching the maximum load, up to the available data point. These achievement can lead to significant time and cost savings for researchers.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors acknowledge the support provided by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (MCIN/ AEI) under project MCIN/AEI/10.13039/5011000011033 (reference PID2020-119015GB-C22). The first author also acknowledges the support from the Generalitat de Catalunya, under the grant IFUdG 21/01, co-funded by Banco Santander. The authors also acknowledge the support from the Generalitat de Catalunya, under the grants 2022_FISDUR ref. BDNS 612831 and 2020_FISDU 00476,

and of the Spanish Government through the grant RYC2021-032171-I funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by European Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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